

Project Acronym: 'EVOLVE'

Project Full Title: Isolation and analysis of extracellular vesicles using optofluidics for the evaluation of microsatellite instability in endometrial cancer

Call: HORIZON-MSCA-2021-PF-01

Type of action: HORIZON-TMA-MSCA-PF-EF

Grant Number: 101069074

This metadata file describes the data on the "[Dataset of Material and Results from the Technical Report of MSCA-PF-2021 EVOLVE](https://zenodo.org/records/14009613)" found at <https://zenodo.org/records/14009613>

- NTA evDNA Chip:

Contains the Nanoparticle Tracking Analysis results for the different functionalization types tested with the evDNA chip. Data per run is found as ".csv" files (opened by standard Microsoft Office Excel), and the analysis results are found as ".pdf" files.

- CAD files:

Two CAD files ("*CAD_2023_10_10 - Herringbone_Mixer_2Layers.dxf*" and "*CAD_2024_04_19_Pillar_chip_80umDiameter_40umGap.dxf*"), in ".dxf" format, present the designs for the Herringbone and Pillar chip devices, respectively. Software for CAD designing is required to open these files.

- ddPCR file:

"*ddPCR_MSI_Test_Hec1A_SW480_RKO_Cells_L-EVs_s-EVs_2024_05_06.ddpccr*" file presents the data from the ddPCR run for MSI detection. This file requires the QX Manager Software from Bio-Rad to be open and accessed.

- DNA sequences:

A Microsoft Office Word document ("*DNA_Synthetic DNA sequences for MSI assessment.docx*") presents the different synthetic DNA sequences designed for the project.

- DNA functionalization:

A Matlab code file ("*Matlab_DNA_Functionalization_Au_Slides.m*") includes the data acquired for the various DNA functionalization and hybridization experiments, also plotting the figures found on the Technical Report for the EVOLVE project. This file requires MATLAB R2018b (or later) to be accessible.

- Origin files:

Two Origin graph files ("*Origin_DNA loss within evDNA Chip.opj*" and "*Origin_evDNA Chip EV-Capture Efficiency.opj*") are included, presenting the data for the DNA loss within the evDNA chip and the different EV capture efficiencies for the different functionalization types tested, respectively. These files require the Origin software to be accessible.